

Aerotoxic Syndrome: A New Occupational Disease?

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KEYWORDS

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ABBREVIATIONS

OP	Organophosphate
TAPs	Triaryl phosphates
TBP	Tributyl phosphate
TCP	Tricresyl phosphate
TPP	Triphenyl phosphate

ABSTRACT

Pyrolyzed oil leaking through engine oil seals and entering the cabin air has prompted debate about exposure hazards to toxic substances. An investigation of ill-health among aircrew involved in contaminated air events was undertaken. Two studies were conducted to review the ill-health of affected aircrew. Findings were compared with published hazard databases, and relevant literature to assess compatibility with known toxicities. Acute and chronic exposures to thermally degraded substances was confirmed and supported by medical findings and diagnoses. We conclude a reasonable link between aircraft air supplies contaminated by engine oil and fluids and ill-health exists.

INTRODUCTION

In the mid-1950s civilian aircraft first started bleeding unfiltered air (so-called bleed air) from engine compressors into the cabin ventilation system. It was promptly recognized that air bled from the engine

compressors was contaminated with engine oil leaking into the cabin ventilation system. Hydraulic and de-icing fluids were also thought to be possible contaminants as a result of being drawn in through the engine air intake. Military studies found that the base stock of engine oils produced a wide variety of toxic substances as temperatures increase, i.e. when pyrolysed.¹ Reports of ill health among flight crew were soon observed.²

Turbine engines utilize synthetic lubricants that generally include an ester base stock (95%), a wide variety of triaryl phosphates (TAPs), organophosphate (OP) anti-wear additives (around 3%), amine antioxidants and proprietary ingredients (1–2%). The commercial formulation of the OP additive is generally cited as tricresyl phosphate (TCP).

Over the last 20 years, many ad hoc air-monitoring studies have been reported during normal engine operations. These have focused on TCP, which is routinely found in 25–100% of air samples taken during flights.³ Tributyl phosphate (TBP) was identified in 73% of flights, while low levels of TBP and triphenyl phosphate (TPP) metabolites have been found in 100% of urine samples.

Over the past two decades, there an increasing number of case studies and reports have been published but, sadly there has been considerable debate and controversy about the sources of contamination, the toxicity of the pyrolyzed volatile organic hydrocarbons and other substances in the bleed air, the consistency of the presenting symptoms and signs and argument about the causal mechanism.^{4–6} The debate about cause and effect seems to center on the observations that if the alleged contaminants are present in bleed air, their concentrations are below industry accepted standards and are, therefore, non-toxic, and that, even in the situation where there is no doubt about contamination, such as when there are visible or non-visible fumes in the cabin, a so-called 'fume event', the symptoms reported by the afflicted are so variable and non-specific, that to accept a single condition/disease as the explanation does not stand the test of scientific scrutiny. Thus,

the reported symptoms have been explained by some as being due to psychological problems, stress and hyperventilation and have been discussed elsewhere.⁷

We report here the results of two separate studies which were designed to determine if the symptoms and signs reported by aircrew exposed to suspected aircraft contaminated air events are consistent with exposure to jet engine oil and engine/aircraft fluids or other factors.

METHODS

Two studies were conducted as follows:

- Study A was undertaken in 2005-2009 and asked the question “What health effects are being reported in UK BAe 146 pilots exposed to contaminated bleed air?”^{8,9}
- Study B was undertaken in 2016 and sought to review well documented aircraft cabin air contaminated incidents to determine if the pattern and effects experienced, by those exposed, were consistent with the expected health effects of exposure to cabin air contaminated with engine oils, hydraulic or de-icing fluids and their pyrolyzed products or other factors.⁹
- Study A reviewed a group of pilots, their workplace environment and general health and specific symptoms.
- Study B differed from Study A in that it identified and addressed 15 separate specific contaminated air events, the associated symptoms and reported health effects per incident, rather than per person, as in Study A.
- Study A was a BAe 146 aircraft pilot health survey. United Kingdom Pilot Unions were requested to supply a list of all known United Kingdom certified BAe 146/146 Avro RJ aircraft (BAe 146) pilots. Attempts were then made to contact all those pilots listed by the Unions in order to conduct a telephone interview or written survey. Data were collected (by SM) from 2005 to 2009 on demographics, flying history, flight deck air quality history, health effects, medical diagnoses and other comments.

- Study B was a case study analysis of 15 potential cabin air quality incidents. The incidents were selected because they were reported to be consistent with acute hyperventilation and hypoxia and extensive data was available.¹⁰ Data sources included: airline, crew and maintenance reports; incident investigation and regulator reports; health effects and medical records; and media, union and legal reports. The incidents took place in Australia, Germany, the United Kingdom and the United States of America. Extensive data on the aircraft flight history, acute and long-term crew effects, medical diagnoses and findings, and maintenance findings were collated.

A table was then developed to categorize acute and chronic symptoms.

Substances utilized in the oils and hydraulic and de-icing fluids were then assessed against the European Regulation EC No. 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances (CLP) hazard classifications and hazard databases.¹¹ Symptoms were compared with published literature on cabin air, hyperventilation and hypoxia.

RESULTS

The results of study A were that contact details of 389 pilot names were supplied by the Unions. This number was 14% of the CAA 2002 licensed BAe 146 pilots. One hundred and fifteen of the 389 pilot details supplied could not be contacted because of the information was incorrect, wrong or out of date information. All 274 pilots contacted took part in the survey, a 70% response rate of the total names listed and 100% of those contacted. One hundred and forty-two reported specific symptoms and diagnoses, 30 reported adverse health effects, but provided no detail, while 77 reported no health effects and 25 failed to advise either way, resulting in 219 (80%) with assessable information.

Eight-eight percent (88%) of respondents were aware of the possible exposure to contaminated air in aircraft

cabins. Thirty-four percent recorded frequent exposures, 18% reported exposure to one-two big events and 7% had experienced visible smoke or mist events. Immediate or long-term health effects were experienced by 63%, whereas 44% reported effects which lasted for a few days or up to about a week (*Figure 1*). These effects included symptoms of chronic fatigue, dizziness, confusion, disorientation, nausea and abdominal pain, headache, memory and cognitive impairment. Sinus and eye irritation and breathlessness and chest discomfort (*Figure 2*).

Operational findings of study B were that the 15 different incidents reviewed involved seven different types of aircraft in four different countries (UK, USA, Germany and Australia), with 53% being in the flight deck alone and 27% in both the flight deck and aircraft cabin. In 80% of events fumes only were detected. All events were reported to occur during non-steady state engine operations with 80% occurring during climb or descent. In 66% of the aircraft involved fume events had been reported either before or after the cases studied here. Maintenance finding reported positive oil leakage detected in 87%.

Medical findings of study B were that various degrees of incapacitation through to significant impairment in flight

was reported in 93% of the events, with the majority (73%) involving the pilots and in 33% both pilots were affected. Adverse health effects were experienced in at least one crew member in 75% of the 15 incidents, while passengers reported adverse effects in 27% of the incidents. In 53% of events, long-term health effects were experienced and in 47% of events 10-23 different symptoms were reported by the crew. Health effects were acute in 66% and chronic ill-health was experienced in 66%. Nine pilots were certified unfit to fly. Symptoms, diagnoses and ill-health effects reported are shown in Table 1.

The records related to Study B and long-term diagnoses are various and as expected based on the wide variety of symptoms experienced and are shown in Table 2.

DISCUSSION

Recognition of bleed air contamination was first reported in the 1950s and all current transport aircraft, except the Boeing 787, use the bleed air system to supply the cabin ventilation requirements. The common use of the engine compressor pressurized air to seal the oil-bearing chamber and as a source for the cabin bleed air supply provides a mechanism for low-level oil leakage in routine engine operations. Low-level leakage of oil

System	Symptoms reported
Neurological	
Central nervous system	Impaired or loss consciousness/headache/physical incapacity/paralysis/loss of balance/ataxia/visual impairment
Peripheral and autonomic nervous system	Tremor/incoordination/paraesthesia/numbness/peripheral neuropathy/sweating/loss of temperature control/pallor/flushing/taste impairment
Cognitive effects	Impaired problem solving Poor concentration Memory and writing issues Giggling/euphoria
Other systems	
Gastrointestinal	Nausea/vomiting/abdominal cramps/bloating
Respiratory	Breathlessness/cough/chest discomfort/wheeze/recurrent respiratory tract infection
Cardiovascular	Chest pain and tightness/irregular heart rate/hypertension
Skin	Rash/photosensitivity/blisters/alopecia
General	Arthralgias/generalised aches and pains/weakness/fatigue/feeling unwell/vocal and nasal symptoms/sinusitis
Malignancy	Various

Table 1 — Study B: Symptoms Reported After a Fume Event Exposure

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RADS/occupational asthma x 6 • PTSD x 3 • Neurotoxic injury x 1 • Toxic encephalopathy x 1 • Neuropathy on vocal chords/limbs x 3 • MCS x 1, CFS x 1 • Anxiety/depression x 1 • Cognitive dysfunction x 4 • Dementia x 1 • ADHD x 1 • Migraines x1 • Seizure disorder x 1 | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depression x 1 • Aerotoxic Syndrome x 1 • Chemical injury at work x 1 • Neurological chemical injury x 1 • CNS injury x 1 • G4 GBM x 1 (deceased) • Wallerian degeneration x 1 • Vocal polyps x 1 • Heart attack + phosphate exposure x1 (deceased) • Frontal lobe damage x1 • Optic nerve damage x1 |
|--|--|

Table 2 — Study B: Long-Term Medical Diagnoses Recorded by Medical Staff

over the engine oil seals into the aircraft air supply at transient phases of flight in normal operations will occur, with less frequent higher level leakage under certain operational conditions, such as seal wear or seal failure.³ While many suggest oil leakage is only associated with rare failure conditions, others are now recognizing that chronic exposure to 'tiny' amounts of oil vapors leaking continuously over the seals occurs with engine power changes.^{3,12,13} Interestingly, the manufacturer of Study A aircraft have acknowledged that all engines leak oil and that their engines used to leak oil greater than the industry average and that there was a general health problem, but no flight safety issue!¹⁴

The experience of ill-health effects and, in some cases, serious clinical outcomes reported in our two studies reported here leads to the conclusion that there is a reasonable link between aircraft air supplies contaminated by engine oil and fluids and the development of acute and chronic ill-health and possible long-term impairment in some of those affected. A clear pattern of repeat low level exposures followed by acute events were identified, supporting acute on chronic effects. These findings suggest a cause and effect relationship. When the Bradford Hill causation criteria are applied to our studies,¹⁵ it is clear that eight of the nine criteria are met with only the dose response criterion not being upheld.⁸

In summary, it is now clear that bleed air from aircraft jet engines leaking into the air-conditioning system is harmful to health and is an important occupational health and safety issue which needs to be seriously addressed by airlines, the aircraft manufacturers and the regulators.

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